

Triterpenoid Constituents of the Seeds of *Diospyros melanoxylon*, *Tecomella undulata* and *Terminalia bellirica*

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*Diospyros melanoxylon*¹ Roxb. (Ebenaceae), *Terminalia bellirica*² (Gaerln) Roxb. (Combretaceae) and *Tecomella undulata*³ G. Don Seem (Bignoniaceae) plants are found in deciduous forests of India. Different parts of the plants are considered useful in folk medicine¹⁻³. Some attention to the chemistry of various parts of *D. melanoxylon*⁴, *T. bellirica*⁵ and *T. undulata*⁶ have already been focussed. We report here our results on chemical examination of the seed extracts of these plants wherein the isolation of some phytosterols, triterpenes and sugar have been accomplished.

Experimental

Seed of the above mentioned plants were collected from forests of Kota and Chittorgarh divisions of Rajasthan by courtesy of Social Forestry Division. Air-dried and coarsely powdered seeds (3 kg) of each of the species were separately extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and ethanol successively. Removal of solvents from the appropriate extracts under reduced pressure yielded semi-solid mass in each case.

Concentrated petroleum ether extracts of all three plants were subjected to column chromatography over Brockmann neutral alumina (deactivated with 10% aqueous glacial acetic acid) and successive elution with petroleum ether, petroleum ether-benzene mixtures (in varying proportions), benzene and ethyl acetate gave various fractions. Each fraction was further purified by preparative tlc using kiesel gel PF₂₅₄, 60F₂₅₄ (Merck) plates and petroleum ether-benzene mixture (1 : 1) as solvent.

Seeds of *D. melanoxylon* afforded following compounds. *β*-Sitosterol : Elution of column with benzene afforded colourless flakes (100 mg), m.p. 135–36°; positive Liebermann-Burchard and Salkowski tests; C₂₉H₅₀O (M⁺ 414); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 400 (OH), 1 050 cm⁻¹ (C–O), and confirmed by preparation of its acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 125–26°. *α*-Amyrin : Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) mixture afforded yellowish solid (50 mg), which on crystallisation from petroleum ether gave colourless needles, m.p. 185–86°; positive Liebermann-Burchard and Noller's tests; C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350 (OH), 2 990–2 885 (C–H), 1 640 (C=C), 1 050 cm⁻¹ (C–O); the acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 222–23°, and confirmed by comparison with an authentic specimen. *β*-

Amyrin : Fractions obtained by eluting column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) gave colourless needles (50 mg), m.p. 196–97°; positive Liebermann-Burchard and Noller's tests; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 380 (OH), 2 990–2 885 (C–H), 1 650 (C=C), 1 050 cm⁻¹ (C–O); the acetate (Ac₂O/Py), colourless plates, m.p. 237–38°, and confirmed by comparing with its ir data. *Betulin* : Fraction obtained by elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) gave yellowish solid (30 mg), colourless needles (benzene), m.p. 248–49°; positive colour tests for triterpenes; C₃₀H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 442); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 460–3 400 (OH), 2 970–2 880 (C–H), 1 650 (C=C), 1 080, 880 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.75 (3H, s), 0.82 (3H, s), 0.96 (3H, s), 0.97 (3H, s), 1.02 (3H, s), 1.68 (3H, s), 3.30 (d) and 3.80 (d, CH₂OH), 3.18 (1H, dd), 2.39 (1H, m), 4.69 (1H, d) and 4.57 (1H, d, vinyl-H), and confirmed by preparing its diacetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 215–16°. *Betulinic acid* : Elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 4) afforded colourless crystals (40 mg); Salkowski reaction; C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺ 456); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 300–2 500, 1 710 cm⁻¹ (COOH); the methyl ester, m.p. 220–21°; ¹H nmr of methyl ester δ (CDCl₃) 0.76 (3H, s), 0.82 (3H, s), 0.92 (3H, s), 0.97 (6H, s), 1.69 (3H, br s), 3.68 (3H, s), 3.34 (CH-O, dd), 4.60 (1H, br s) and 4.74 (1H, br s, vinyl-H), and confirmed by co-tlc and co-ir with an authentic samples.

Seeds of *T. undulata* yielded following compounds. *β*-Sitosterol : Elution of column with petroleum ether gave white flakes (100 mg), colourless flakes (CH₃OH + CHCl₃, 1 : 1), m.p. 136–37°, and identified as *β*-sitosterol as above. *ε*-Sitosterol : Fraction obtained by elution of column with petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) gave white solid (20 mg) which on crystallisation from (CH₃OH + CHCl₃, 1 : 1) afforded needles, m.p. 142–44°; Liebermann-Burchard test for sterols, C₂₉H₅₀O (M⁺ 414); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 400 (OH), 1 052 (C–O), 950 cm⁻¹, and confirmed by preparing its acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 127–28°. *Taraxerone* : Elution of column with a mixture of petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1), afforded colourless crystals (30 mg), C₃₀H₄₈O (M⁺ 424), m.p. 249–50°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 050, 1 720 (C=O), 1 640 (C=C), 820 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 0.84 (3H, s), 0.93 (6H, s), 0.96 (3H, s), 1.08 (3H, s), 1.10 (6H, s), 1.15 (3H, s), 2.45 (2H, m), 5.34 (1H), and identified by comparison with sample of taraxerone. *Friedelin* : Elution of column with

petroleum ether-benzene mixture (1 : 3) afforded yellowish solid (25 mg), $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (M^+ 426), m.p. 265–67°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 cm^{-1} (C=O); 1H nmr δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.73 (3H, s), 0.88 (3H, s), 0.89 (3H, d), 0.97 (3H, s), 1.01 (6H, s), 1.05 (3H, s), 1.18 (3H, s), and confirmed by reduction with $NaBH_4$ to epifriedelinol, m.p. 276–77°. *Betulin* : Elution of column with benzene afforded a yellowish solid (40 mg), m.p. 247–48°, which was identified with betulin obtained from *D. melanoxylon*.

Friedelin was also obtained from the seeds of *T. bellirica* along with previously reported compounds and identified by the methods as detailed above.

From the alcoholic extracts of the seeds of each plant, galactose, glucose, fructose, mannose and sucrose were identified by paper chromatography using n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as the spray reagent⁷.

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